

INFORMATION SHEET FOR CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN A RESEARCH STUDY

We are a research team from the University of Macau. We are requesting your participation in a research study titled "Impact of Online Community Involvement on Safety Practices and Perceived Risks Among People Who Use Drugs." You were selected as a possible participant because you are a recreational drug user and speak English. Please read this information sheet and contact me to ask any questions that you may have before agreeing to take part in this study.

Purpose of the Research Study: The purpose of this study is to gain insights into how people who use drugs interact with online communities, and to understand the impact of these interactions in order to help users stay safer.

Procedures: If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to answer questions about your personal experiences with drug use, how you interact with online communities, the perceived impact of these interactions, which features you find appealing, and any privacy concerns you may have.

Risks and Benefits of Being in the Study: The risk of the study is that some questions about your substance use might be uncomfortable to answer. Your participation can help inform the development of tools that may benefit and be appreciated by many people. You need to be aware that using recreational drugs might be illegal in your country. If information about your drug use is disclosed, it will result in criminal charges. As researchers, we will use the following methods to ensure that your information will not be disclosed. First, we will not ask for any personal information that may be used to identify yourself. You can ask us to remove any information that you mentioned during the interview afterward. Second, we will keep all data confidential. The data will be stored in an encrypted device. Only the research team will have access to it. The data will be kept for five years and will be destroyed immediately after the preservation period.

Compensation: You will be compensated for your time and participation in this study with an equivalent of 50 USD.

Voluntary Nature of the Study: Participation in this study is voluntary. Your decision whether or not to participate will not result in penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. If you decide to participate, you are free to not answer any question or discontinue participation at any time without penalty, or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Length of Participation: The study will take 60 minutes to complete. If unforeseen circumstances arise such that either you or the researcher cannot complete the interview in one setting, we may arrange a second or subsequent meeting to complete the survey.

Confidentiality: The records of this study will be kept private and your supervisor will not have access to your responses. In published reports, there will be no information included that will make it possible to identify you as a research participant. Research records will be stored securely. All data be kept on password protected computers in the researcher's laboratory. Written documents will be kept in the researcher's possession. Only approved researchers will have access to the records. We will keep the data for five years. After the completion of the storage period, all data will be destroyed. You are able to withdraw their interview data two weeks after the interview.

Contacts and Questions: If you have any questions, concerns, or complaints about the research or about your rights, the researcher(s) conducting this study can be contacted at wangye.macau@gmail.com. In the event of a research-related injury, please contact the researcher(s). You are encouraged to contact the researcher(s) if you have any questions.

*Please keep this information sheet for your records. **By completing and submitting this consent form, I am agreeing to participate in this study.***